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**TEACHERS' QUALITY ASSURANCE PRACTICES FOR THE
IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR SECONDARY GOVERNMENT IN
NSUKKA EDUCATIONAL ZONE, ENUGU STATE**

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Abstract

The study assessed Government teachers' quality assurance practices in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum. Three research questions and one hypothesis (tested at 0.05 level of significance) guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The sample consists of 13 SS2 Government teachers and 291 SS2 Government students drawn from Nsukka Education Zone. Questionnaires were used for data collection. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while hypothesis was tested using independent t-test statistic. The findings of the study revealed that Government teachers to a high extent possessed requisite knowledge of the subject matter, and to a high extent made use of communication skills. It was also found that teaching experience had significant influence on the quality assurance practices of Government teachers. It was recommended among others that workshops and seminars should be organized by the relevant Agencies of Government on regular basis for teachers to help them improve on quality assurance practices in teaching and learning government in schools.

Keywords: Quality assurance, quality assurance practices, knowledge of subject matter, classroom communication skill, and teaching experience.

Introduction

Quality assurance in education aims at enhancing quality of teaching and learning, especially with respect to improving learners' achievement, standards, personal skills and participation. It dwells largely on quality of the curriculum and related activities, quality of care, guidance and safety, quality of the learning environment and the effectiveness of leadership and management (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2015:14). Quality assurance therefore is the process of obtaining evidence that teachers who teach the various school subjects including Government are effectively implementing the contents of subject in secondary

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school Quality assurance practices are what teachers do to ensure quality teaching and learning through effective curriculum implementation in the classroom. To ensure quality implementation of Government curriculum, there is the need to check quality assurance practices of Government teachers. The key issues in the Quality Assurance document for quality teaching and learning include Teachers' knowledge of the subject matter, classroom communication skills, Teacher's experience, lesson plan, etc. (FRN, 2015). In this study, teachers knowledge of the subject matter, classroom communication skills and teachers experience constitute the major focus.

Knowledge of the subject matter refers to the extent to which a teacher has good knowledge or mastery of the subject he or she teaches. According to Okolocha and Onyeneke (2013) adequate knowledge of the subject matter is necessary and essential for teaching and learning process to be effective in the classroom. Therefore, Government teachers need to have good knowledge of the contents of Government for them to teach well. Good knowledge of the subject implies having the content knowledge of the subject. However, knowledge of the subject matter in Government is not enough for effective teaching and learning of Government. It must be accompanied with good communication skill for the Government curriculum to be effectively implemented.

Communication is the process of passing information among people (Okwo, 2009). According to Ismail and Idris (2007), it is effective classroom communication that ensures effective teaching and learning. The way Government teachers pass information to students is one of the many factors that could determine whether or not teaching and learning is effective. Therefore, Government teachers need to possess effective classroom communication. These skills could be in verbal form, namely short talks, discussions, and jokes and non-verbal forms such as gestures and facial expressions that would enable teachers to convey contents adequately in the classroom. Hence, quality assurance practices in curriculum implementation, in this study, entail teachers' knowledge of the subject matter and application of classroom communication skills in teaching of Government subject.

Government is one of the elective subjects under Humanities studied in senior secondary school. Government is generally defined in three ways: namely Government as an institution of state, Government as a process or art of governing, and Government as an academic field of study (Anyaele, 2003; Nigerian Education Research and Development Council (NERDC), 2007). However, the focus of this study is on Government as an academic field of study in secondary schools. Government as an academic field of study suggests that

Government is a subject that is studied in Senior Secondary school, at the senior level and other institutions of higher learning through which the students are taught the mechanism by which people are governed in a state. According to NERDC (2007) the objectives of Government as a school subject are:

to enable the students: understand the concepts, principles, institutions and process of government, recognize his role as conscious and knowledgeable citizens and his contribution towards the realization of national development, to participate actively in the democratic process of national and their local governments, understand the role of Nigeria as a member of international community, understand the challenges and dynamics of past and present government in Nigeria and the world, and recognizes the role of ICT in e-government and in fostering the process of government in the world (p. i)

The above lofty objectives of Government as a field of study in secondary school cannot be achieved or realized without proper compliance with the quality assurance practices in curriculum implementation. In spite of the introduction of the quality assurance in the educational system by the government of Nigeria and the affirmation that it is the key to effective implementation of various subject, it seems that teachers have not been living up to expectations with respect to expected best practices (Ozuode, 2021).

The poor implementation of quality assurance in secondary schools does not only manifest in the dwindling academic performance of secondary school students in external examinations but also in non-realization of the objectives of certain subjects including Government. One of the objectives of Government as a subject is to enable students become active participants in democratic process in the society. However, in spite of many years Government has been taught in schools, the political culture of Nigerians, especially, with respect to participation in democratic process still remain low. It has been observed by some scholars that one of the major problems besetting Nigeria's political system in recent times is political apathy or lack of interest in political affairs of the country (Nwaubani, Anyikwa & Azuh, 2014). The low political culture does not promote democratic process, nation building and national transformation. According to Jega (2018), there is a very tenuous relationship between the democracy and nation-building. It is only a stable democracy that can foster nation-building and national transformation in a country. Thus, low political culture brings about not only bad

leadership but also bad followership. In retrospect Nweke (2015) observed that any democracy driven by bad leadership adversely affects nation-building. This shows that the subject is yet to achieve the goals for its introduction in secondary schools. This situation also applies to quality assurance practices in the implementation of Senior secondary school government curriculum. Teachers' constitutes one of the major determinants of quality of education in any country. It is based on the importance of teachers in education that it was declared in the National Policy on Education that "no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers" (FRN, 2014, p. 64). Arising from the foregoing, this study investigated the extent to which Government teachers comply with the quality assurance practices in the implementation of Government curriculum in public secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone, Enugu state. The study specifically focused on teacher's knowledge of the subject matter, application of classroom communication skills and teaching experience respectively.

Teaching experience is one of the factors that could determine the effectiveness of teachers in curriculum implementation (Owolabi & Adedayo, 2012). According to Oyewole (2011), a highly experienced teacher has a form of knowledge that surpasses that possessed by a less experienced teacher. Teaching experience is the knowledge or skill acquired through teaching over a period of time. Teaching experience of a teacher is usually measured by the number of years a teacher has been teaching. Teachers generally in terms of experience can be classified into two namely; Experienced and non-experienced. However, most often, studies refer to experienced teachers as those who have taught for approximately 5 years or more while inexperienced or less-experienced teachers are those with less than five years teaching experience (Owolabi & Adedayo, 2012). Similarly, in this study, "experienced" teachers refer to teachers who have taught Government for five or more years while those with less than five years of teaching experience are referred to as "inexperienced" or less experienced teachers. Some studies such as Oyewole (2011) and Owolabi and Adedayo (2012) have shown that teaching experience is one of the factors that could influence teachers' performance in the classroom and consequently affect students' academic performance. On the contrary, Papay and Kraft (2015) showed that teaching experience, under some circumstances, does not actually promote teacher effectiveness in schools. Hence, in these studies, the influence of teaching experience on Government teachers' compliance with the quality assurance practices in the implementation of Senior secondary school Government curriculum was examined.

Statement of the Problem

One of the objectives of Government as a subject is to enable students to become active participants in democratic process in the society. However, in spite of many years Government has been taught in schools, the political culture of Nigerians, especially, with respect to participation in democratic process has been low. It has been observed by some scholars that one of the major problems affecting Nigeria's political system in recent times is political apathy or lack of interest in issues that concern government in the society. As a result, the leaders take advantage of the peoples' lack of interest in democratic process to retard systematic and sustainable development. This shows that Government as a subject is yet to achieve the goals for its introduction in secondary schools. Researchers have attributed this to non-compliance by teachers to prescribe quality assurance practices in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum. Arising from the foregoing, this study investigated the extent to which Government Teachers comply with the quality assurance practices in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum in public secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone, Enugu state.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do teachers possess requisite knowledge of the subject matter for quality assurance in implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum?
2. To what extent do teachers make use of communication skills for quality assurance purpose in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum?
3. What is the influence of teaching experience on quality assurance practices of Government teachers for effective implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum?

Research Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant difference in the quality assurance practices of experienced and less experienced teachers in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum.

Method

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted in secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State. The population of the study was made up of 1145 respondents, consisting of 76 Government teachers, and 1069 Senior Secondary 2 (SS2) students offering Government in the sixty (60) public secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone. The sample size of the study was 13 Teachers and 291 SS2 Government students. Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to draw the sample. The instruments for data collection were two questionnaires: namely, teachers' Questionnaire titled Questionnaire on Government Teachers' Awareness and Quality Assurance Practices in Curriculum Implementation (QGTAQAPCI) and Students' Questionnaire titled Questionnaire on Government Teachers Quality Assurance Practices" (QGTQAP). The two questionnaires were developed by the researchers based on the issues raised in the objectives of the study and key issues for assessing quality teaching and learning as outlined in the quality assurance document (FRN, 2015). The face validation of the instrument was carried out to ensure that questionnaire items were relevant to the purpose of study and the research questions. The Cronbach Alpha internal consistency reliability coefficients of the instruments were 0.91 and 0.89, respectively. The research instruments were administered to the respondents by the researchers and two trained research assistants through direct delivery method. Data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions while independent t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent do teachers possess requisite knowledge of the subject matter for quality assurance implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum?

Table 1: Mean ratings and standard deviation of responses of Government students on teachers' knowledge of the subject matter for quality assurance in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum

S/N	Item statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remarks
1	My Government teacher explains clearly what we are expected to learn from every topic at the beginning of each lesson.	3.31	0.654	HE
2	My Government teacher does not explain the subject contents very well with emphasis from different textbooks	2.92	0.809	HE

3	My Government teacher has deep interest/enthusiasm in the subject	3.04	0.821	HE
4	My Government teacher does not take time to explain difficult ideas/topics in the subject	3.25	0.706	HE
5	My Government teacher gives different point of view of the topics discussed in the subject.	2.88	0.828	HE
6	My Government teacher does not allow discussion on content of the subject to current events in society	2.98	0.809	HE
7	My Government teacher uses many examples to explain topics in Government lessons.	2.92	0.830	HE
8	My Government teacher's explanation of the topics in Government always corresponds with textbook explanations.	2.98	0.707	HE
Cluster mean		3.03	0.77	HE

NB: VHE = Very High Extent; HE = High Extent; LE = Low Extent; VLE = Very Low Extent

The responses of Government students in table 1 indicate that the teachers to a high extent have knowledge of the subject matter for quality assurance in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum, as shown by the cluster mean scores of 3.03. Item by item analysis shows that all the items in the table were rated to a high extent (with corresponding mean scores of 3.31, 3.04, 2.88, 2.92, and 2.98 respectively).

Research Question 2: To what extent do teachers make use of communication skills for quality assurance purposes in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum?

Table 3: Mean ratings and standard deviation of responses of Government students on teachers' use of communication skills for quality assurance purpose in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum

S/N	Item statements	Average	Standard Deviation	Remarks
9	My Government teacher communicates clearly in the class	3.05	0.951	HE
10	My Government teacher explains the lesson very well and we understand it easily	2.86	0.951	HE

11	My Government teacher does not answer students' questions in the class satisfactorily	3.30	0.758	HE
12	My Government teacher maintains friendly facial expression while teaching	2.86	1.033	HE
13	My Government teacher is not heard by everybody in the class while teaching	3.08	0.993	HE
14	My Government teacher maintains good facial contact with students in the classroom	2.91	0.783	HE
15	My Government teacher applies good gestures like nodding of head, patting students back as a way of encouraging good answers by students	3.08	0.788	HE
16	My Government teacher uses words that are confusing while teaching	2.96	0.953	HE
Cluster mean		3.01	0.90	HE

NB: VHE = Very High Extent; HE = High Extent; LE = Low Extent; VLE = Very Low Extent

The responses of Government students in table 3 indicate that the teachers to a high extent make use of communication skills for quality assurance purpose in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum as indicated by the cluster mean score of 3.01. Item by item analysis shows that item 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16 were all rated to high extent with corresponding mean scores of 3.05, 2.86, 3.30, 2.86, 3.08, 2.91, 3.08, and 2.96 respectively.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of experience on quality assurance practices of Government teachers for effective implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum?

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation of the influence of experience on quality assurance practices of Government teachers for effective implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum

Group	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean difference
Less experienced	3	160.00	6.245	22.3
Experienced	10	182.30	11.634	
Total	13			

The data presented in Table 5 shows that the experienced teachers had mean quality assurance practices scores of 160.00 and standard deviation of 6.245 while the less-experienced teachers had a mean quality assurance practices score of 182.30 and standard deviation of 11.634. The result showed that means quality assurance practices score of experienced teachers is higher than that of their counterparts with a difference of 22.3. This implies that there is difference between the quality assurance practices of experienced and less-experienced teachers and also suggests that experience had influence on the quality assurance practices of Government teachers for effective implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the quality assurance practices of experienced and less experienced Government teachers in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum.

Table 6: Mean, standard deviation and independent t-test analysis of the quality assurance practices of experienced and less experienced Government teachers in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum.

Group	N	Average	Std Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remarks
Less experienced	3	160.00	6.245	-3.121	11	.010	Significant
Experienced	10	182.30	11.634				
Total	13						

Table 6 shows that t value (-3.121) has a probability value of .010. Since this value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the quality assurance practices of experienced and less experienced Government teachers in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum. Experienced Government teachers had higher quality assurance practice score (M = 182.30, SD = 6.245) than less experienced Government teachers (M = 160.00, SD = 11.634). The mean difference was significant, $t(11) = -3.121$, $p < .05$.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study with respect to research question one showed that Government teachers to a high extent possessed requisite knowledge of the subject matter for quality assurance in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum. This is because there are existing documents on quality assurance practices which teachers are aware of. The finding of this study is in consonance with Nwona and Madu (2018) which found out that Physics teachers had good content knowledge of the subject. Similarly, Nwona and Madu (2018) revealed that Physics teachers had mastery of the content of Physics and were able to teach it well. This finding also corroborates Omebe's (2015) assertion that a good teacher should have good mastery of the knowledge of contents of the subject he/she teaches.

Result of the study with respect to research question two showed that Government teachers to a high extent make use of communication skills for quality assurance purposes in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum. One of the most important attributes of a good teacher, according to Omebe (2015), is to be a good communicator. Hardly is there a class in which the teacher does not communicate with the students in one way or the other. It is effective communication that promotes effective teaching and learning in classroom (Ismail, & Idris, 2007).

Result of the study with respect to research question three showed that teaching experience had significant influence on the quality assurance practices of Government teachers in effective implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum. This is largely so because experience counts in every profession including teaching. Thus, teachers who have taught Government for more than five years are likely to show more mastery of content and related quality assurance compliance than those with less number of years of teaching experience. The finding of the study is supported by Oyewole's (2011) which revealed that teachers' years of experience had significant influence on job performance of secondary school teachers in Ekiti State, Nigeria. According to Oyewole, the more experienced teachers tended to perform better than the less experienced ones. However, this finding contradicts the findings of some studies such as Papay & Kraft (2015), which revealed that academic performance of learners taught by inexperienced teachers seem not as good as those taught by experienced teachers. That is teachers with more teaching experience are not necessarily in all circumstances more effective than their inexperienced or less experienced counterparts.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that Government teachers to a high extent possessed requisite knowledge of the subject matter and do make use of communication skills. There is therefore effective quality assurance with respect to teachers' subject matter knowledge and use of effective communication skill in the implementation of Senior secondary school Government curriculum. Similarly, teaching experience had significant influence on the quality assurance practices of Government teachers in the implementation of senior secondary school Government curriculum. Therefore, the problem of poor performance in Government at external examinations could be as a result of being taught by less experienced teachers.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of the study it was recommended that:

1. Regular workshops, seminars and conferences should be organized by Government in collaboration with other professional stakeholders or regulatory bodies for serving teachers on ways of deepening Government teachers quality assurance practices.
2. Effective mentoring mechanism should be put in place in senior secondary schools to help more experienced teachers to assist their less experienced counterparts on quality assurance related matters with respect to effective implementation of Government curriculum.

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